
A Study on Parents' Aspirations and Their Role in the Education of Students of Upgraded Middle School

Dr. Shabana Jabeen Warsi

Assistant Professor, L.K.Mishra College of Teacher Education Darbhanga

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20682393>

ARTICLE DETAILS	ABSTRACT
<p>Research Paper</p> <p>Accepted: 19-05-2026</p> <p>Published: 10-06-2026</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords:</p> <p><i>Parental Aspirations, Role of Parents, Educational Development, Upgraded Middle School, Parental Involvement.</i></p>	<p>The study highlights that parental guidance, awareness and encouragement are essential for the overall development and educational progress of children. The study was based on the belief that education is necessary for becoming responsible citizens and that parents' aspirations greatly influence the future achievements of children. The present study adopted the Exploratory Research Method along with a Qualitative Approach to obtain detailed information regarding parents' aspirations and involvement in their children's education. Data were collected through a semi-structured interview schedule. The population of the study included all parents of upper primary students studying in the upgraded middle school. A sample of 15 parents was selected through the Purposive Sampling Technique. The study included parents from different genders, religions, castes, educational backgrounds, occupations and income groups to obtain diverse perspectives regarding children's education and parental roles. The findings of the study revealed that 100 percent of parents wanted to admit their children to High School Anandpur for secondary education, indicating their trust in the institution. Parents expressed different aspirations for their children, including becoming good human beings, attaining higher education, getting government jobs, becoming doctors, engineers or soldiers and overcoming poverty. The study further revealed that all parents had arranged tuition for their children's education and many parents</p>

personally guided their children in studies. Some parents, despite poor economic conditions, made extraordinary efforts to support their children's education. The findings also indicated that parents considered education important for social welfare, development, elimination of social evils and reduction of poverty. The study further highlighted parents' expectations regarding improvement in the quality of education, computer education, English language teaching, Mid-Day Meal facilities and safety arrangements in schools. The majority of parents participated in Parent-Teacher Meetings and ensured that their children attended school regularly. Overall, the study concluded that parental aspirations and involvement have a strong influence on the educational development and future success of children.

Introduction

Parents play an irreplaceable role in the lives of their children. This relationship has a profound impact on the child's mental, physical, social and emotional development, as well as their overall health and happiness. Parents support us at every stage of life. The relationship between parents and their children affects children not only in childhood but throughout their lives. It affects all areas of a child's life, such as health development, educational progress and professional opportunities, as well as life choices.

One of the main roles of parents is to provide encouragement, support and access to activities that enable the child to master important developmental tasks. A child's education and socialization are most influenced by their family because the family is the child's primary social group. Providing and supporting a child with an education is one of the important landmarks in a child's development. A good education will help the child to have a rewarding career and thus contribute positively to society. Parents are also their children's biggest cheerleaders and give them unconditional love.

According to NCFTE 2009-:

Education is likewise the gateway to the world and the display of infrastructure is incomplete without an assessment of the extent to which it opens doors for children in rural India. According to the NCFTE 2009 document, after independence, 82% of the 200 million children aged 5 to 14 were in school in India, according to a government report, of which about 50% drop out before completing the eighth grade. Traditionally, the socio-economic status of the family, such as the income level of the parents and

the level of education of the parents, have been considered as predictors of children's academic achievement. Educational research has suggested that rather than being a direct correlation between children's academic achievement, socio-economic status and children's level of education are psychological and social variables that affect children's school outcomes. Attendance at higher levels of education may be a means of accessing resources, such as income, time, energy and community connections, that allow for greater parental involvement.

Child Rights and Education as per the Constitution of India:

Free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of 14 years is a constitutional commitment in India. At the time of adoption of the Constitution in 1950, the aim was to achieve the goal of Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) within the next 10 years, i.e. by 1960. At that time, the facilities available in the country were far from the short target of 10 years.

Therefore, the target date was shifted several times. Till 1960, all efforts were focused on the provision of school facilities. After the target of access was approached, other components of UEE, such as universal entry and retention, started to receive the attention of planners and policy makers. It is the standard of education, which is currently the focus of all programmes related to elementary education in general and primary education in particular. Providing free and compulsory education to all children up to the age of 14 years is a constitutional obligation. In 1993, the Supreme Court of India declared education, which is the fundamental right of children in India up to the age of 14 years. The entire school education can be divided into four parts, namely, primary, upper primary, secondary and higher secondary levels. The National Policy on Education 1986 and its revised formulation 1992 envisaged a uniform pattern of school education i.e. (10+2) in all states. Since education is in the Harmonized List, the States and UTs are free to develop their own framework of school education. The 8 years of primary education are conceived in 2 stages: a junior stage which covers a period of five years and a senior stage which has a period of three years. It is important to mention that the eight years of compulsory education were conceived as a coherent unit although there were two stages of this cycle hence elementary education became an integral part of India

Basic Duties: Article Under A51(K): According to the Constitution of India, it is one of the fundamental duties of every parent to provide education to their child between the ages of 6 to 14 years.

Operational definition

Parental Aspirations

Parental aspirations refer to the aspirations of parents of students studying in upgraded middle schools for their children’s education.

An illiterate child going to school is considered a great achievement, bringing about a qualitative change in the parents’ lives. The attention paid by parents to their children’s education is continuously increasing in the pursuit of education across the socio-economic segments of the population. Although parental educational aspirations play an important role in shaping and influencing student aspirations, achievements and attainment, our understanding of the nature and structure of these important aspirations is limited. Researchers have always examined parental educational aspirations as an independent variable rather than a dependent variable. Educational aspirations play an important role in educational attainment.

Role of parents

The role of parents here refers to the parents whose children are studying at Up-Grade Middle School. The role of parents plays an important role in today's educational development. Such as taking proper care of their health, their physical development, their overall education, their intellectual and attachment development as well as a better moral values.

(Need and Rational of the study)

In a changing society, education is a must and parental guidance is needed in getting education. Maintaining a good relationship between parents and children is very important for wise parents. Upper primary education is the foundation of secondary education and basic education improves further education. At this stage, the role of parents plays a major role in shaping the future of children. To

become a better citizen, it is necessary to be educated, and in this process parental awareness and purposeful thinking are essential. Parental guidance is also necessary for the all-round development of children because children learn their first lessons of discipline, morality and responsibility from their parents. In a developed country, parents must trust their children and support their desires so that they can achieve the best in their respective fields. Education is considered the most powerful weapon that can be used to change the world, and therefore parental awareness becomes highly important in ensuring that children receive proper education and opportunities for growth. The Indian Constitution recognizes the role of parents through several constitutional provisions related to the welfare and education of children. Article 15(3) allows the State to make special provisions for children in order to ensure their protection and development. Similarly, Article 39(e) and Article 39(f) emphasize that the State shall ensure that childhood and adolescence are protected against exploitation and against moral and material neglect. These constitutional provisions collectively highlight the importance of parental responsibility and the commitment of the State to safeguard the rights, dignity and future of children. Such provisions indicate that the development of children is not only the duty of parents but also a shared responsibility of society and the government. Article 51A Clause (k) of the Indian Constitution further emphasizes the responsibility of parents and guardians toward the education of children. It states that parents or guardians of children between the ages of six and fourteen years must provide opportunities for education to their children. This constitutional duty reflects the importance of parental involvement in ensuring that every child receives elementary education and develops into a responsible citizen. It also recognizes education as a fundamental requirement for national development and social progress. According to the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, the active involvement of parents in their child's education is highly important. The policy aims to establish a strong partnership between parents, teachers and schools in order to improve the quality of education and ensure the holistic development of children. NEP 2020 emphasizes Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE), parental participation in school management, awareness regarding educational opportunities and better communication between parents and teachers through technology. The policy promotes play-based and activity-based learning approaches that make education more engaging and meaningful for children. It also encourages the formation of School Management Committees and flexible educational systems that empower parents to take informed decisions regarding their children's education. Through these initiatives, the policy recognizes parents as important stakeholders in the educational process and highlights their role in building an educated and progressive society.

Objectives of the study

1. To know the educational aspirations of the parents of the students studying in Upgrad Middle School regarding their children.
2. To study the role of the parents of the students studying in Upgrad Middle School in the educational development of their children.

Research Questions

1. What are the educational aspirations of parents of students studying at the upgraded middle school?
2. What is the role of parents of students studying at the upgraded middle school in the educational development of their children?

Review of the related literature

Anitha, M(2017) conducted a study titled Parental aspiration on their children education study on govt. school The specific objective of this study was to study the aspirations of parents regarding their children's education and also to determine the attitude of parents towards the infrastructure and availability. To carry out this study, the researcher asked some questions from the parents of the students through interviews to collect data. For this, 13 government schools were taken. For this, the researcher used the survey method. This study found that the occupation of the parents shows that one-third of the mothers were daily wage laborers, two-fifths of the fathers were daily wage laborers, their monthly income was 2500 to 5500, and a large proportion of the mothers were married below the age of 20. More than half of the parents were of the opinion that the school should be good. More than half had arranged tuition for the guidance of the child. A bad part of the parents wished that education was necessary for them. Two-thirds of the illiterate mothers said that teachers occasionally visited the students' homes. Rahman & Biswas(2022) conducted a study titled. Parents attitude and perception towards primary education A study in rural West Bengal of India. In which the parents here are not economically strong and the most important thing is that they trust the government school and clearly state that many of them have succeeded who were educated in government schools. The school buildings are much better than the mission at that time. The aim of this study is to study the role of parents in increasing the quality of education of primary school students - and secondly to study the relationship between parents and teachers in increasing the quality of education - for this, the researcher used the stratified random sampling method. For this, the researcher took 100 male and female students. From this study, the researcher found that a large number of parents send their children for tuition. On both occasions, an

inequality has emerged among children. Educated parents say that children learn better than children of ignorant parents. Jacob, M(2010) .conducted a study titled Parental Expectation and aspirations for their children's educational attainment: and examination of the college-Going mindset among parents, which aimed to and expectations. In addition to examining parent reports, the study included 598 parents of 8th-10th grade students from five schools in Meadowlands. Parents were administered the Educational Expectations and Expectations Scale. They were also asked to answer several questions about their college knowledge. After factor analysis, the items reflecting aspirations and expectations loaded on a single factor; all of our further experiments revealed a small but significant difference between these two beliefs. The results also revealed a gap between parents' aspirations and expectations for their children's educational achievement and their knowledge of what it would take to make that dream a reality. Strengths, limitations, implications for research and practice, and directions for future research are discussed. Vryonides,M.& Gouviyas,D(2012) A study entitled Parents' aspirations for their children's educational and occupational prospectus in Greece: The role of social classThe study focuses on parents and the way they perceive and shape expectations. In this, parents have aspirations for their children's educational and occupational outcomes. A survey conducted among more than 700 parents of primary school students shows that an interesting pattern can be observed in parents' aspirations. This can be partly explained by differences in the social and cultural capital of parents circulating in the home environment.The discussion of the findings is based on the argument that families often use different strategies as a result of their society. Positioning is related to specific social and cultural characteristics that shape the achievement or understanding of a particular habit. This study examines the hidden mechanisms that often originate from the family and social class differentiation in education that perpetuate overall social inequality and thereby idealize equality in education.Ahmad et al ,. (2010)Parental aspirations appear to be one of the most important predictors of children's educational and social development, especially in decision-making for children's tertiary education. This study identifies parental attitudes towards engaging in the enhancement of children's education among parents of secondary school students in Selangor. The factors of interest are: parental income and ability, children's financial readiness for tertiary education, children's involvement in activities in schools and children's performance on future careers. The results positively showed that parents are paying more attention to their children's educational future in terms of decisions, expectations and finances.Kumar, B. (2023). conducted a study titled "A Study on the Effect of Parental Involvement, Educational Aspirations and Habits on the Academic Achievement of Scheduled Caste Secondary School Students". Scheduled Caste "Scheduled Caste" is a socio-economically backward group of the society and occupies the lowest position in the caste hierarchy in the entire country. The objective of this study is to know the educational

aspirations and aspirations of the parents of Scheduled Caste students. And to study the educational aspiration of Scheduled Caste secondary school students. To study the academic achievement of secondary school students. To carry out this study and to collect the data, the researcher has used “Stratified Random Probability Sampling Method”. In this study, 760 Scheduled Caste students who are residents of Jammu and Kashmir have been selected as the sample. The results of this study show that there is a significant difference in the mean score of parental involvement of Scheduled Caste secondary school students with their respective gender. Furthermore, the results of the study show that there is no significant difference in the average score of the academic aspirations of Scheduled Caste secondary school students according to their respective gender. Furthermore, the results of the present study indicate that there is a significant positive effect of parental involvement on the academic achievement of Scheduled Caste secondary school students. Mahamood et al. (2010) conducted a study titled “A Study on Parental Involvement Among Four Students in Selangor”. Parents’ aspirations regarding their children’s education Parental involvement in future educational planning is defined as the extent to which parents provide resources and energy to their child in a specific developmental, positive and educational area through which their child can achieve success in the future. To conduct this study and to obtain data, the researcher developed a questionnaire for parents using the random sampling method. For this study, questionnaires were distributed to 560 students through which data was collected. In this study, the parents of the students were to answer various questionnaires. The questionnaires were based on the demographic profile of the students. Most parents felt that the school should be good. More than half of the children had arranged tutoring to guide them. Parental involvement was found to be a positive and powerful source of influence on the achievement of adolescents. Parents should be further encouraged by the school to be more involved, which can have a positive impact on the academic achievement of students. Oketch, M. et al. (2012). This study sought to examine the differences in parental aspirations for their children’s educational attainment (as a measure of parental involvement in children’s education) between slum and non-slum parents in Kenya. This study used cross-sectional household data for a sample of 4065 parents, collected in 2007 by the African Population and Health Research Centre (APHRC) in Nairobi. A multivariate logistic model was used for analysis to explore the determinants of parental aspirations. The results indicate the following: (i) that parents living in slums have lower aspirations for their children’s educational attainment than those living in non-slum areas. (ii) that parents in slums have higher aspirations for their children’s educational attainment than their own level of education. We conclude that parents in urban Kenya strongly believe in their children’s education regardless of whether they live in slums or non-slums, but their aspirations are higher in non-slums than

in slums. Alam, J & Ogawa, K(2023)conducted a study titled "Parental Aspirations for Children's early childhood education enrollment in Bangladesh"- The aim of this study was to examine the aspirations of parents who motivate their children to enroll in higher education. To conduct this study, the researchers used a case study methodology. To conduct this study, the researchers studied 68 parents as well as various government documents. The results show that parental aspirations, concerns, social and economic conditions significantly influence children's enrollment in higher education. The study argued that parental aspirations for children's enrollment and non-enrollment in ECE are obstacles to social justice in education for all children. Finally, all stakeholders should take innovative policy measures to ensure institutional justice and equal enrollment opportunities for children aged 3-5 years.Sharma, Chetna (2020)conducted a study titled Educational aspiration among secondary school students in relation to their perceived parental encouragement and psychological wellbeing. The aim of this study was to study the educational aspirations of the students in relation to their perceived parental encouragement and psychological wellbeing. The study was conducted in ten districts of Punjab namely, Doba, Malwa and Majha. Based on the area and type of school, the study was limited to 500 secondary school students. A self-developed tool was used to measure educational aspirations while the scale of Dr. Kasum Agarwal (2019) was used to measure parental encouragement. Thus, for the measurement of psychological wellbeing, Dr. Devendra Singh Sisodia and Ms

Methodology

Research In the present study, Exploratory Research Method has been adopted to better understand the research problem. The aim of this research method is to know the different aspects of the problem in depth and to understand the thoughts, experiences and opinions of the people concerned. Qualitative Approach was used to collect data, because through this method, the thoughts and experiences of the parents can be understood easily and in detail. In this study, researcher used semistructure interview schedule for the information was obtained through questions and discussions so that the real situation related to the subject could be revealed. The population of this study included all the parents of the upper primary level students of the upgraded middle school. Since parents play an important role in the educational development of children, their opinions were made the main part of the research. 15 parents of students studying in the upper primary level were selected as the sample. These parents were included on the basis that they were directly related to the research topic and could present their opinions in a better way. The present study used the Purposive Sampling Technique as the Sampling Method. Under this technique, the researcher selected parents from the population who were suitable for the research objectives. This method helped in making the research more effective.

S. No	Class	Total Parents
1	6	2
2	7	6
3	8	7

S.No.	Variables		No. of Sample	Total
01	Gender	Male	06	15
		Female	09	
02	Religion	Hindu	12	15
		Islam	03	
03	Caste	Brahmin	05	15
		Sahni	01	
		Dhobi(H)	02	
		Raeen(M)	02	
		Jaiswal	03	
		Roy	01	
		Shah(M)	01	
04	Parents' Qualification	Illiterate	02	15
		Schooling	08	
		Graduation	03	
		PG	02	
05	Parents' Occupation	Unskilled	05	15
		Skilled	05	
		Govt. Job	02	
		Self-Business	03	
06	Parents' Income (Annually)	Up to 60K	05	15
		60K to 120K	05	
		120K to 260K	03	
		Above 260K	02	

Explanation:

To carry out this project, the researchers selected 15 parents of students studying in the Upgrad Middle School, Harpalpatti, out of which 12 were from Hindu and three from Muslim communities. In this study, the number of respondents, that is, 9 were females and 6 were males, of which two respondents were from Muslim community and the remaining 7 were from Hindu community. To carry out this study, the researchers have conducted an exploratory nature study. In this study, the qualitative method has been used to collect data. In this study, the data includes parents from different castes of both communities, which include 5 Brahmins, 3 Jaishwals, 2 Dhobi (Hindu), 2 Rai (Muslim), 1 Rai (Hindu) and 1 Muslim (Shah) - in which the level of family life of the parents ranges from low to higher education. The annual income of the parents has been divided into four stages by the researcher, looking at the ground level. In this study, the professional level of parents has been divided into four stages. The total number of children of the parents is 57, of which 34 are girls and 23 are boys. Out of these children, 18 girls and 11 boys are studying at UMS

Classification by caste of the respondent

Respondent's status of parents' occupation

Respondent's classification by religion

Respondent's gender

Respondent's education classification

Classification by annual income of the

After the researcher's research, it was revealed that 100 percent of parents want to admit their children to High School Anandpur. This shows that all parents consider this school suitable for their children's secondary education. The research revealed different views about the expectations of parents from their children. 13 percent of parents said that their children will become good human beings. 33 percent of parents hope that their children will do something good in life. 33 percent of parents want their children to get higher education, while 20 percent of parents hope that their children will overcome poverty and improve their economic condition. Parents' wishes regarding the future and position of their children also differ. 40 percent of parents want their children to get a government job. 20 percent of parents want their children to become doctors and engineers. One parent wants their children to become soldiers, while 33 percent of parents said that they will fully support whatever their child wants to become. Regarding parents' aspirations regarding education, 27 percent of parents believe that education is very important for the well-being of the society. 20 percent of parents said that development can be achieved only by getting education. According to 13 percent of parents, education can eliminate social evils, while 40 percent of parents say that education can remove poverty. Regarding the efforts of parents for the educational development of their children, it was found that 100 percent of parents have arranged additional tuition for their children's education. 60 percent of parents also guide their children themselves along with tuition. Seven percent, that is, the mother of a child whose husband has passed away, even begs for her child's education. After meeting a child's guardian, it was found that they can manage their family's expenses by working for five days, but they work for seven days so that their children get a good education. Regarding the knowledge about the fundamental duties of the Constitution, 40 percent of the

people in this study responded that they do not know about the fundamental duties of the Constitution. While 60 percent of the people also said that they do not know about the fundamental duties of the Constitution. But when the researcher told them about the Constitution, 100 percent of the people said that in the social context they know that it is mandatory for us to send children to school. Regarding the expectations of parents from the school for the educational development of their children, 53 percent of the people said that this school should have computer education. 20 percent of the parents believe that the quality of Mid-Day Meal (MDM) should be improved. 60 percent of the people said that the quality of education should be improved, while 33 percent of the people said that the teaching of English language in schools should be better. Regarding safety in school, 40 percent of the parents said that the boundary wall of the school should be high and teachers should be supervised while crossing the main road. Regarding parental involvement in school, 54 percent of the respondents said that they attend parent-teacher meetings when they are held in the school. 26 percent of the respondents said that they occasionally attend PTM, while the rest do not attend PTM. Regarding sending children to school on time, 80 percent of the respondents said that they send their children to school on time, while 20 percent of the students go to school occasionally, out of which one child also studies in a private school. Regarding the number of girls being more than boys in school, 54 percent of the respondents said that they send their boys to private schools, while 40 percent of the respondents said that they cannot say anything about why the number of girls is more in school.

Finding and Conclusion

After the researcher's research, it was revealed that 100 percent of parents want to admit their children to High School Anandpur. This shows that all parents consider this school suitable for their children's secondary education. The research revealed different views about the expectations of parents from their children. 13 percent of parents said that their children will become good human beings. 33 percent of parents hope that their children will do something good in life. 33 percent of parents want their children to get higher education, while 20 percent of parents hope that their children will overcome poverty and improve their economic condition. Parents' wishes regarding the future and position of their children also differ. 40 percent of parents want their children to get a government job. 20 percent of parents want their children to become doctors and engineers. One parent wants their children to become soldiers, while 33 percent of parents said that they will fully support whatever their child wants to become. Regarding parents' aspirations regarding education, 27 percent of parents believe that education is very important for the well-being of the society. 20 percent of parents said that development can be achieved only by getting education. According to 13 percent of parents, education can eliminate social evils, while 40

percent of parents say that education can remove poverty .Regarding the efforts of parents for the educational development of their children, it was found that 100 percent of parents have arranged additional tuition for their children’s education. 60 percent of parents also guide their children themselves along with tuition. Seven percent, that is, the mother of a child whose husband has passed away, even begs for her child’s education.After meeting a child’s guardian, it was found that they can manage their family’s expenses by working for five days, but they work for seven days so that their children get a good education.Regarding the knowledge about the fundamental duties of the Constitution, 40 percent of the people in this study responded that they do not know about the fundamental duties of the Constitution. While 60 percent of the people also said that they do not know about the fundamental duties of the Constitution. But when the researcher told them about the Constitution, 100 percent of the people said that in the social context they know that it is mandatory for us to send children to school. Regarding the expectations of parents from the school for the educational development of their children, 53 percent of the people said that this school should have computer education. 20 percent of the parents believe that the quality of Mid-Day Meal (MDM) should be improved. 60 percent of the people said that the quality of education should be improved, while 33 percent of the people said that the teaching of English language in schools should be better.Regarding safety in school, 40 percent of the parents said that the boundary wall of the school should be high and teachers should be supervised while crossing the main road.Regarding parental involvement in school, 54 percent of the respondents said that they attend parent-teacher meetings when they are held in the school. 26 percent of the respondents said that they occasionally attend PTM, while the rest do not attend PTM.Regarding sending children to school on time, 80 percent of the respondents said that they send their children to school on time, while 20 percent of the students go to school occasionally, out of which one child also studies in a private school.Regarding the number of girls being more than boys in school, 54 percent of the respondents said that they send their boys to private schools, while 40 percent of the respondents said that they cannot say anything about why the number of girls is more in school.

References

- Alam, D. M., & Ogawa, K. (2023, June). Parental aspirations for children's early childhood education enrolment in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, Vol. 12 (No. 2), 1136-1144. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369334545>
- Gain, M. R., Biswas, S., & Dev, P. (2022, April). Parents Attitude and Perception towards Primary Education ;Astudy in Rular Wesat Bangal of India. pp. 15(01):4276-4295.

- Jacob, M. J. (2010, June). Parental Expectations and Aspirations for their Children's Educational Attainment: An Examination of the College-Going Mindset among Parents. University of Minnesota. Retrieved from https://conservancy.umn.edu/bitstream/handle/11299/93924/Jacob_umn_0130E_10989.pdf?sequence=1
- Kasturiragan. (2020, July). National Education Policy . Retrieved from https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf
- Kumar, B. (2023). A study of influence of parental involvement, educational aspiration and study habits on academic achievement of scheduled caste secondary school students. Central University of Kashmir. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/136646>
- Kumar, N. (2018). Effect of parental involvement Educational aspirations and family Climate on academic achievement of Secondary school students. Department of Education Maharshi Dayanand University. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/299341>
- M.Anitha. (2017). Parental aspiration o their childrens education - A study on government schools. shodhganga@INFLIBNET.
- Mahmood, S. F., Saat, A., Tapsir, R., & Ahmad, S. (2012). Parental Attitude and Involvement in Children's Education: A Study on the Parental Aspiration among Form Four Students in Selangor. *Procedia - Social and behavioural science*, 42, 117-130. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042812010555>
- Oketch, M., Mutisya, M., & Sagwe, J. (2012, November). Parental aspirations for their children's educational attainment and the realisation of universal primary education (UPE) in Kenya: Evidence from slum and non-slum residences. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 32(6), 764-772.
- Sharma, & Chetna. (2020). Educational aspirations among secondary school students in relation to their perceived parental encouragement and psychological well being. Department of education Punjab University Chandigarh. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/305580>
- Siddiqui, M. A., Sharma, P. A., & Batra, P. (2009). National Curriculum Framework For Teacher Education. Retrieved from https://ncte.gov.in/website/PDF/NCFTE_2009.pdf
- Vryonides, M., & Gouvias, D. (2012, december). Parentsa aspirations for their childrens educational and occupational prospects in Greece : The role of social class. *Interational journal of Educational Research*, 0883-0355.